

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

Report on the application hackathon with an assessment of the role of SR-ESMs in improving climate projections and providing input to international agreements (e.g. the Paris Climate Accord). The focus will be on the oceanic component, and on aspects such as the passive uptake of heat and carbon by the ocean.

Work package in charge:

WP7

Lead author:

Johann Jungclaus

Other contributing authors:

Arjun Kumar

Internal reviewer(s):

1st reviewer: Marcus Dengler

2nd reviewer: Markus Jochum

Contacts: johann.jungclaus@pimet.mpg.de

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Executive summary

The Hackathon was organized in March 2024 in Hamburg under the lead of the Storms and Oceans theme as a collaborative event together with the Horizon-Europe-funded EERIE and the German BMBF-funded WarmWorld projects. In addition to these projects, we welcomed a group from MPI-M and Hamburg University. This group works specifically on ocean biogeochemistry and the carbon cycle in the framework of the H2020 ESM2025 project and Hamburg University's Cluster of Excellence CLICCS using the HAMOCC biogeochemistry module. The focus of the Hackathon was an assessment of the newly available NextGEMS Cycle 4 experiments in comparison with previous cycles and the EERIE simulations. During the preparation of the Hackathon intensive cooperation took place among the projects to ensure that the simulation data were in place ahead of time and that a comprehensive set of tools for data assessment and evaluation was available. NextGEMS simulations were made available via catalogues in the innovative HEALPix format that allows users to assess the data at different resolutions. The application Hackathon addressed the specific question whether it is important to resolve meso- and submesoscales in the ocean models in climate simulations. To include a larger community working on aspects of eddy-resolving models, NextGEMS joined forces with EERIE to assess the role of eddies in transient climate change simulations. Furthermore, in collaboration with the HAMOCC group the participants analyzed additional simulations with interactive ocean biogeochemistry that allowed the role of eddies and storms for air-sea exchanges to be investigated. In particular, the group studied the uptake/release of anthropogenic carbon at fronts or underneath cyclones and their role in triggering/damping phytoplankton blooms. Other topics pursued during the Hackathon followed the work schedule of the individual work packages in the Application Phase. A task-force concentrated on a bug in the sea-ice module of ICON and successfully eliminated a bug in the sea-ice ocean interface. The Storms & Society group conducted social network analyses on the participant's interactions within the hackathons and continued their work on knowledge co-production and dissemination.

Figure 1: The Cycle 4 hackathon participants in front of the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology in Hamburg

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	yes
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	yes
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	yes
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	yes
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	yes

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP7	Relevance in this deliverable?
To identify the importance of meso-scale air-sea interaction on tropical climate, on its dominant patterns of variability and teleconnections, and on its response to global warming (O1,O2)	yes
To appraise the significance of resolving atmospheric convection and storm-scales for simulating the West African Monsoon (WAM) and hydrological cycle extremes, and their response to global warming (O1,O2)	yes
To evaluate the influence of mesoscales on tropical cyclones and on their response to global warming. (O2)	yes
To assess the impacts of climate and climate change on global primary productivity, and global and West African fisheries using SR-ESMs (O1,O2,O3)	yes
To anticipate the relevance of resolving mesoscale circulations for global climate change assessments (O1,O2,O3)	yes
To evaluate and refine new ocean mixed layer and planetary boundary layer representation in the coupled system (O1)	yes

Synergies

The success of the hackathon was based on strong links between nextGEMS and the partner projects EU Horizon EERIE and ESM2025 and the German WarmWorld project. Furthermore the link to the French and Senegalese fishery communities that was established during hackathon 3 was further developed and it was discussed how SR ESMs can improve the simulation of coastal upwelling and forecasts of fish abundance in African coastal waters.

1 The fourth km-scale Hackathon

The hackathon was organized by S&O and designed as a joint event together with the H2020 EERIE and the German WarmWorld projects. Particular fruitful additional input came from the H2020 ESM2025 project, who provided ICON simulations that allowed the participants to include aspects of ocean biogeochemistry. In addition to scientists and technical staff from nextGEMS, EERIE, WarmWorld, and ESM2025, modelling experts and scientific programmers from MPI-M and AWI joined the hackathon. Planning of the event had started late 2023 after the EERIE hackathon in Bremerhaven (November 2023) had taken place with several nextGEMS partners involved. The meeting took place at the MPI-M and the neighboring Hamburg University.

137 participants from 17 countries attended the hackathon, with 60 (44%) coming from nextGEMS and 77 coming from 14 different projects. 61% were early career scientists (Bachelor/Master students, PhD candidates, Scientists up to 6 years after PhD) and 28 % were senior scientists. The remaining 10 % counting other backgrounds or occupations. The nextGEMS office gave ten travel grants to attendees from low-income countries or students from other projects.

The hosting projects provided several new simulations to the hackathon. Apart from nextGEMS' cycle 4 simulations, there were several EERIE experiments available. An overview on the data material can be found on the [easy.gems website](https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/nextGEMS/joint_hackathon.html)

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In the weeks before the hackathon preparations were done by the technical staff to provide the data of cycle 4 simulations in the catalogue system. As a novel feature, both ICON and IFS/FESOM data were made available in the HEALPIX format to allow the participants to download gridded data at various resolutions. The individual work packages had organized themselves beforehand and defined their goals ahead of time. The weekly nextGEMS Science Hours were used to introduce these goals and to share information on available experiments and tools.

Similar to the previous hackathons, the participants organized themselves in working groups, partly along the lines of the nextGEMS themes, partly reflecting additional interests, e.g., the sea-ice error in ICON. The "knowledge co-production" theme brought together a community of scientist working on the role of the mesoscale in the ocean. A particular focus was on analyzes regarding the importance of ocean eddies for climate simulations, and on storm and eddy-related aspects of air-sea interactions, including the exchange of carbon.

The work at the hackathon forms the basis for a nextGEMS overview paper Segura et al., 2025.

The hackathon began Monday afternoon with introductory talks on the progress made from cycle 3 to cycle 4 in ICON and IFS/FESOM, new technical aspects, and a presentation on EERIE models and experiments. This was followed by presentations laying out the plan for the week in the working groups. The afternoon was concluded by a keynote talk by Prof. Daniela Jacobs from the German Climate Service Center on the Earth Virtualization Engines (EVE) initiative.

During the week, most of the time was dedicated to hacking with a few get-togethers including a keynote talk by the newly appointed MPI-M director Sarah Kang on the topic "Possible shifting mechanisms for the tropical Pacific surface warming pattern". A "world-café" session was included on Tuesday to discuss general questions of storm and eddy-resolving numerical experimentation and their role in climate change assessment.

The meeting ended on Friday with a wrap-up session, where the working group results were presented, following by a general discussion.

1.1 Storms & Radiation

The S&R group worked on process-based evaluation of the energy budgets and the interactive aerosols in ICON simulated with an aerosol module by the University of Oxford. A first group analyzed cycle 4 simulations focusing on low-level clouds in the tropics and characteristic properties of convective updrafts and precipitation cells in IFS and ICON (see Figure 2), which is based on the identification of deep convective cores in the simulations as strong updrafts at 500hPa. This is shown as composite of the air vertical velocity around those cores. In ICON, convection is simulated explicitly and therefore compensating subsidence is expected to occur around the updraft. The red curve shows the theoretical subsidence in the cloud environment. The fit is overall very good, except close to $x=0$ where there is the updraft (and therefore strong ascending values). This discrepancy is expected because the theory is intended to represent the downward motion of clear air around the updraft, and not inside the updraft. In IFS, convection is partly parameterized and therefore one does not expect any local compensating subsidence as this is partly handled by the parameterization. Therefore there is only weak vertical motion around the updrafts, and it is mostly ascendant which we can hypothesize to be caused by a higher likelihood to form updrafts in large scale ascending regions.

Figure 2: Analysis of updrafts in ICON and IFS.

An issue of particular concern is the simulated internal variability in ICON. The cycle 4 simulation ngc4008 exhibits very weak ENSO and MJO variations. It turned out that the ENSO amplitude is more realistic in the test simulation with 5km resolution in both ocean and atmosphere (ngc4008 has 10km in the atmosphere), which might give a hint to convective processes that are either resolved or not in the atmosphere. The work started here forms a basis of a new working group

at MPI-M studying ENSO characteristics in ICON simulations at different resolutions. A second group analyzed a year-long simulation with interactive aerosols focusing on the tracking of dust storms over Africa and the understanding of aerosol activation across the globe (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Tracking of dust storms in the Sahara.

1.2 Storms & Land

The S&L group worked on diurnal variability over land in storm resolving models and the soil moisture-precipitation feedback. They analyzed surface fluxes in ICON and IFS/FESOM from different simulations/cycles. In the transient cycle 4 simulations the group investigated changes in blocking frequency and the occurrence of heat wave under climate change. They found a strong increase in blocking events over Europe in the coming decades and regional diverse trends in heat wave risks with a hot spot around the Mediterranean Sea.

Also, the surface radiation balance over land has been re-evaluated based on the new Cycle 4 runs. In an earlier hackathon, the S&L group discovered large biases in downwelling shortwave radiation in ICON that lead to an overestimation of turbulent fluxes (heat and moisture) over land. Many of these biases have been solved in the Cycle 4 runs, bringing also the surface radiation climate over land for ICON and IFS closer together.

1.3 Storms & Ocean

The ocean team continued working along the lines of the WP 7 task description assessing the newly available cycle 4 simulations with respect to atmospheric teleconnections, the monsoon systems, air-sea interactions and the tropical boundary layers in ocean and atmosphere. Analyzing mean state biases, it was found that deficits in the representation of precipitation in the Tropics and the global monsoon regions are likely related to SST biases. These occur more pronounced in the ICON ngc4008 run compared to IFS/FESOM. Investigating aspects of variability in IFS/FESOM, a group focused on the MJO and on African Easterly Waves and extended the analyses to climate change in the IFS/FESOM simulation. While some trends could be identi-

fied, it turned out to be difficult to attribute the changes to global warming, because no proper control simulations was available with the same model system. Work on Tropical Cyclones (TC) continued studying TCs in the cycle4 transient simulations from IFS/FESOM. Continuing work from the 2023 hackathon, where “fisheries” was a knowledge co-production topic, the group from Senegal investigated how upwelling-productivity is constraining pelagic fish stocks and fisheries using ICON-O simulations with HAMOCC ocean biogeochemistry. The simulated productivity trends are similar to the observed ones, thereby bolstering the efficacy of ICON/HAMOCC for prospective applications in fisheries (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Results from the ICON-O simulation including ocean biogeochemistry show consistent trends in observations and model

The ocean tropical mixed-layer and mixing group (Task 7.5) analyzed the occurrence of near-inertial waves (NIW) and Tropical Instability Waves (TIW) in the ICON and FESOM cycle 4 simulations. Building on experience gained from nextGEMS stand-alone ocean simulations from Task 6.5, analyzes were carried over to the coupled experiments from cycle 4. NIW appear to be realistically simulated in ICON, but are generally weaker compared to observations. Ongoing work aims at comparing “typical” TIW and NIW events from observations (nextGEMS D6.3) to the model results and to investigate the imprint of TIWs on the overlying atmosphere.

1.4 Eliminating a bug in ICON’s sea-ice model

The hackathon offered a unique opportunity to focus attention on a problematic issue that was detected in the ICON cycle 4 runs. Occasionally, large holes appeared in the Arctic sea-ice cover in summer. Such ice-free patches are not realistic and were never seen in earlier ICON experiments at lower resolution. A task force was established at the beginning of the hackathon consisting of nextGEMS scientists and ocean/sea-ice modelling experts from MPI-M and AWI. First, it turned out to be useful to compare ICON experiments with respective IFS/FESOM runs at similar resolution. The comparison revealed that ICON featured much more energetic ocean currents in the central Arctic than FESOM and that those eddy-rich structures destroyed the sea-ice cover. This led the group to find a bug in the ICON code after relatively short time. It turned out that a logical flag was incorrectly set in the ICON ocean model, whereby the ocean did not feel friction from the sea ice above. The recapitulation of code history further revealed that this bug was introduced many years ago, but never caused obvious problems, because its effect became only apparent at high, eddy-rich resolution. The successful detection and removal of the bug is a major achievement of the hackathon as it benefited from the unique setting and

were (partly) suppressed by filtering, were analyzed and additional AMIP-type experiments were provided by the EERIE project. The joint EERIE/NextGEM group evaluated properties of specific filters used to smooth the ocean output and concluded that scale-dependent filtering should be a preferred option.

A particular focus was on the co-evolution of the ocean and atmosphere in the presence of storms and oceanic eddies with an emphasis on the exchange of carbon.

Figure 6: A tropical cyclone in the ICON simulation run with ocean biogeochemistry. The time/depth plot on the right shows the evolution of ocean's stratification and the phytoplankton concentration before and after the stirring through the tropical cyclone.

Here it turned out to be extremely useful that the MPI-M/Hamburg University ocean biogeochemistry group had provided a coupled ICON experiment including the HAMOCC module at 5km resolution in the ocean. One group used an eddy-tracking software (adapted to ICON and IFS/FESOM during the November EERIE hackathon) to analyze the ocean-atmosphere exchange of carbon and biogeochemical properties within eddies and the integrated effect along the tracks. Another group has investigated the effect of storms on air-sea exchanges and monitored the carbon flux and properties along a tropical cyclone track (Figure 6). This is a unique study that was made possible by the nextGEMS model set-up. Further research will include storms in the Southern Ocean and their importance for carbon uptake.

While exciting progress was made in process understanding and several “for the first time” papers will be written, it turned out to be difficult to assess aspects of climate change. While the cycle 4 transient simulations (2020 to 2049) cover a period of pronounced global warming, it turned out to be difficult to discriminate between the global warming signal, model trend, and internal variability. Some analyzes were also hampered by prevailing biases in the simulations, such as the very strong cold bias in ICON's cycle 4 simulation. Moreover, limited computational resources allowed only one experiment per model system to be carried out. Therefore, there is no control simulation available. Combining nextGEMS run with simulations from EERIE was also not straightforward, as partly different model versions or parameter settings had been applied.

2 Conclusion

Having built on the experience of the previous three hackathons, the participants appreciated the more and more smooth and direct ways of assessing the data using the catalogue system and the healpix output format. Progress was demonstrated in many aspects along the NextGEMS cycles and the 30-year long cycle 4 simulations provided an opportunity to assess aspects of transient global warming. A stark focus on the role of the mesoscale for climate simulations was made possible by continued cooperation with the Horizon Europe EERIE project, profiting from work initiated at the EERIE hackathon in November 2023. The participants reported on exciting results regarding the process understanding at unprecedented resolution in a global model. In particular, following the hackathon's objective, the role of the mesoscale in the ocean was emphasized in analyzes of air-sea interactions, teleconnections, and the uptake of carbon in a simulations with storms and eddies. However, assessing the role of the high resolution in the ocean model for climate change assessments remained challenging. Firstly, the transient simulations from 2020 to 2049 include a global warming signal, but it was difficult to discriminate between forced signal and internal variability. Secondly, the experimental protocol does not include a corresponding control experiment under constant forcing, and thirdly, comparing the nextGEMS simulations with those from EERIE for other time periods turned out to be difficult because sometimes other versions of ICON or IFS-FESOM had been used there.

Lessons learned:

Science

- Outreach to and collaboration with EERIE and ESM2025 was instrumental to broaden the experimental data base and to foster collaboration between the communities.
- 30-year-long storm and eddy resolving simulations provide new insights in climate variability
- New features like the interactive aerosol module in ICON provide innovative insight in processes like dust storms in a global context.
- km-scale simulations including ocean biogeochemistry allow the community to investigate the process of air-sea interactions at fronts and underneath storms and may alter the view on carbon uptake in the ocean.
- The progress is hampered by remaining model biases.
- Assessment of the climate change signal in 30-year transient simulations (2020 - 2050) turned out to be difficult.

Technical

- The catalogue system and the healpix output worked well and was well received by the participants.
- The hackathon benefited from a previous joint hackathon-style meeting with EERIE ocean scientist. Analysis tools like eddy-tracking and spatial filtering was available or could easily be extended to specific needs for the NextGEMS questions.

- Pre-hackathon training sessions were instrumental to have participants start from a common base and provided guidance for preparations and individual preparation for the work.

3 References

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